

Supplementary Table 1. Functional testing of *NR5A1*/SF-1 missense variants in classic cell models using promoter activation reporter assays.

Study number	Location	<i>NR5A1</i> /SF-1 variant	Cell line												Transactivation studies																
			Non-steroidogenic						Steroidogenic						Promoter reporters (%) ¹										Dominant-negative effect	Synergistic activation ²					
			HEK293(T)	Tsa201	COS7	COS1	E14	CHO	HeLa	KGN	NCI-H295R	TM3	TM4	Y1	SMAT1	TESCO	STAR	AMH	INHA	CYP11A1	CYP19A1	CYP17A1	HSD3B2	INSL3			DAX1				
1 (1)	N-ter	c.13T>G; p.Tyr5Asp															0	60	60	10						No	ND				
2 (2)		c.17A>G; p.Asp8Gly													120												No	No added effect (SRY/SOX9)			
3 (3)	DBD	c.43G>A; p.Val15Met															40		20	20			20			No	10% activation (EGR1)				
																				60											
																					40										
																					40										
4 (2)																0										ND	No added effect (SRY/SOX9)				
5 (4)																0	40			20		0	40			ND	ND				
6 (5, 6)			c.58G>C; p.Val20Leu*																	0		0	0			No	ND				
																						10									
7 (7)			c.64G>A; p.Gly22Ser*																	30						ND	ND				
8 (8)			c.65G>A; p.Gly22Asp*																	40						ND	ND				
9 (5)		c.70C>T; p.His24Tyr*																	0		0	20			No	ND					
																					10										
10 (9)		c.71A>T; p.His24Leu*																	10		0	10			ND	ND					

118 (13)		c.1100A>G; p.Glu367Gly	■															50	50					ND	ND		
119 (13)		c.1109G>A; p.Cys370Tyr*	■															40	50					ND	ND		
120 (44)		c.1126C>T; p.Leu376Phe		■														40						ND	ND		
121 (2)		c.1138G>T; p.Asp380Tyr	■									0												ND	No added effect (SRY/SOX9)		
122 (4)		c.1198G>A; p.Ala400Thr	■									100	120					100		120	100			ND	ND		
123 (8)		c.1259T>C; p.Leu420Pro		■														40						ND	ND		
124 (21)		c.1279C>T; p.Arg427Trp*	■															0		0				ND	ND		
125 (13)		c.1289G>T; p.Ser430Ile	■															50	60					ND	ND		
126 (3)		c.1310T>A; p.Leu437Gln	■															40	20	20			20	No	20% activation (EGR1)		
						■													80								
								■												100							
									■											60							
127 (2)		c.1310T>A; p.Leu437Gln	■									0											ND	No added effect (SRY/SOX9)			
128 (21)	C-ter	c.1379A>G; p.Gln460Arg*	■															70		80			ND	ND			

DBD, DNA binding domain; HR, hinge region; LBD, ligand binding domain; ND, not determined; ter, terminus.

*Reported variant in the *SF1next* study; ¹Promoter reporter activity as shown in graphs or text; ²Activation of promoter reporters with other proteins compared to SF-1 alone.

Supplementary table 2. Functional studies of *NR5A1*/SF-1 missense variants for gene and protein expression, nuclear transfer localization, binding to target genes, as well as *in silico* structure prediction.

Study number	Locatio	<i>NR5A1</i> /SF-1 variant	Protein expression (Western-blot) ³	Nuclear transfer localization (IF)	Binding to target genes (EMSA)	Structure prediction (<i>in silico</i>)
1 (1)	N-ter	c.13T>G; p.Tyr5Asp	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
2 (2)		c. 17A<G; p.Asp8Gly	Similar	Nucleus	ND	ND
3 (3)		c.43G>A; p.Val15Met	ND	Extranuclear foci	Impaired (to <i>Cyp11a</i>)	ND
4 (2)		c.43G>A; p.Val15Met	Similar	Subnuclear foci	ND	Atypical
5 (4)		c.43G>A; p.Val15Met	ND	Subnuclear foci	ND	Atypical
6 (5, 6)		c.58G>C; p.Val20Leu*	Similar	ND	ND	Atypical
7 (7)		c.64G>A; p.Gly22Ser*	Similar	Subnuclear foci	Impaired (to <i>CYP11A1</i>)	Atypical
8 (8)		c.65G>A; p.Gly22Asp*	ND	ND	ND	ND
9 (5)	DBD	c.70C>T; p.His24Tyr*	Similar	ND	ND	Atypical
			ND	ND	ND	ND
10 (9)		c.71A>T; p.His24Leu*	Similar	ND	ND	ND
11 (10)		c.74A>G; p.Tyr25Cys	ND	Partially impaired nuclear localization	ND	ND
12 (11)		c.76G>A; p.Gly26Arg*	Reduced	Partially impaired nuclear localization	ND	Typical
13 (12)		c.77G>C; p.Gly26Ala	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
14 (13)		c.86C>A; p.Tyr29Lys	Similar	Subnuclear foci	ND	ND
15 (9)		c.88T>A; p.Cys30Ser*	Similar	ND	ND	ND
16 (5)	c.90T>G; p.Cys30Trp*	Similar	ND	ND	Atypical	

17 (14)	c.95G>A; p.Ser32Asn	Higher	ND	ND	ND
18 (15)	c.95G>A; p.Ser32Asn	ND	ND	ND	ND
19 (7)	c.95G>A; p.Ser32Asn	Similar	Subnuclear foci	Impaired (to <i>CYP11A1</i>)	Atypical
20 (16)	c.98G>C; p.Cys33Ser	ND	Subnuclear foci	Impaired (to <i>Cyp11a</i>)	ND
21 (2)	c.98G>C; p.Cys33Ser	Similar	Subnuclear foci	ND	Atypical
22 (17)	c.104G>A; p.Gly35Asp*	ND	ND	ND	ND
23 (15)	c.104G>A; p.Gly35Asp*	ND	ND	ND	ND
24 (18)	c.104G>A; p.Gly35Asp*	ND	Cytoplasm	ND	Atypical
25 (13)	c.104G>T; p.Gly35Val	Similar	Nucleus	ND	ND
26 (17)	c.106T>C; p.Phe36Leu	ND	ND	ND	ND
27 (14)	c.115C>T; p.Arg39Cys	Higher	ND	ND	ND
28 (19)	c.116G>C; p.Arg39Pro	Similar	ND	ND	ND
29 (2)	c.116G>C; p.Arg39Pro	Similar	Subnuclear foci	ND	Atypical
30 (20)	c.118A>C; p.Thr40Pro	Higher	ND	Impaired (to <i>Amh</i>)	ND
31 (21)	c.119C>G; p.Thr40Arg	ND	ND	ND	ND
32 (22)	c.122T>G; p.Val41Gly	ND	ND	ND	ND
33 (21)	c.140A>G; p.Tyr47Cys	ND	ND	ND	ND
34 (11)	c.142A>C; p.Tyr48Pro	Reduced	Nucleus	ND	Typical
35 (23)	c.162C>A; p.Ser54Arg	ND	ND	Normal (to <i>Cyp11a</i>)	ND
36 (11)	c.163T>G; p.Cys55Gly	Reduced	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
37 (24)	c.184C>T; p.Arg62Cys	ND	ND	ND	ND
38 (25)	c.187A>C; p.Lys63Gln	ND	ND	ND	ND

39 (14)	c.194G>A; p.Cys65Tyr*	Higher	ND	ND	ND
40 (11)	c.205C>G; p.Arg69Gly	Reduced	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
41 (11)	c.206G>A; p.Arg69His	Reduced	Partially impaired nuclear localization	ND	Atypical
42 (3)	c.234G>A; p.Met78Ile	ND	Extranuclear foci	Impaired (to <i>Cyp11a</i>)	ND
43 (2)	c.234G>A; p.Met78Ile	Similar	Subnuclear foci	ND	Atypical
44 (26)	c.234G>A; p.Met78Ile	ND	ND	ND	ND
45 (27)	c.250C>T; p.Arg84Cys*	ND	Nucleus	Impaired (to <i>Cyp21</i>)	ND
46 (16)	c.251G>A; p.Arg84His*	ND	Nucleus	Partial (to <i>Cyp11a</i>)	ND
47 (2)	c.251G>A; p.Arg84His*	Similar	Cytoplasm	ND	Typical
48 (18)	c.251G>A; p.Arg84His*	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
49 (5, 6)	c.268G>C; p.Gly90Arg*	Higher	ND	ND	Atypical
50 (15)	c.272G>A; p.Gly91Asp	ND	ND	ND	ND
51 (3)	c.271G>A; p.Gly91Ser*	ND	Nucleus	Impaired (to <i>Cyp11a</i>)	ND
52 (2)	c.271G>A; p.Gly91Ser*	Reduced	Subnuclear foci	ND	Atypical
53 (28)	c.275G>A; p.Arg92Gln*	ND	ND	ND	Atypical
54 (3)	c.275G>A; p.Arg92Gln*	ND	Nucleus	Partial (to <i>Cyp11a</i>)	ND
55 (2)	c.275G>A; p.Arg92Gln*	Similar	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
56 (29)	c.275G>A; p.Arg92Gln*	ND	ND	ND	ND
57 (30)	c.274C>T; p.Arg92Trp*	ND	ND	Impaired (to ND)	Atypical
58 (31)	c.274C>T; p.Arg92Trp*	ND	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
59 (32)	c.308G>A; p.Arg103Gln*	ND	ND	ND	ND

60 (33)	c.340C>T; p.Arg114Trp	ND	ND	ND	ND
61 (34)	c.341G>A; p.Arg114Gln	ND	ND	ND	ND
62 (4)	c.368G>C; p.Gly123Ala	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
63 (35)	c.368G>C; p.Gly123Ala	ND	ND	ND	ND
64 (23)	c.386C>T; p.Pro129Leu	ND	ND	Normal (to <i>Cyp11a</i>)	ND
65 (4)	c.386C>T; p.Pro129Leu	ND	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
66 (35)	c.386C>T; p.Pro129Leu	ND	ND	ND	ND
67 (36)	c.392C>T; p.Pro131Leu	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
68 (4)	c.407C>T; p.Pro136Leu	ND	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
69 (7)	c.428G>A; p.Ser143Asn	Similar	Nucleus	Normal (to <i>CYP11A1</i>)	ND
70 (37)	c.437G>C; p.Gly146Ala*	ND	ND	ND	ND
71 (2)	c.437G>C; p.Gly146Ala*	Similar	Nucleus	ND	ND
72 (27)	c.437G>C; p.Gly146Ala*	ND	ND	ND	ND
73 (24)	c.460G>A; p.Ala154Thr	ND	ND	ND	ND
74 (2)	c.493G>C; p.Gly165Arg	Similar	Nucleus	ND	ND
75 (15)	c.503C>A; p.Ala168Glu	ND	ND	ND	ND
76 (33)	c.517G>A; p.Val173Met	ND	ND	ND	ND
77 (36)	c.571C>T; p.Arg191Cys	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
78 (23)	c.593C>T; p.Pro198Leu	ND	ND	Normal (to <i>Cyp11a</i> 3' SF1 site)	ND
79 (33)	c.598C>T; p.Pro200Ser	ND	ND	ND	ND
80 (33)	c.628C>T; p.Pro210Ser	ND	ND	ND	ND
81 (33)	c.632A>G; p.Tyr211Cys	ND	ND	ND	ND

82 (36)	c.634G>A; p.Gly212Ser	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
83 (13)	c.634G>A; p.Gly212Ser	Reduced	Nucleus	ND	ND
84 (38)	c.689T>G; p.Leu230Arg	Similar	ND	Impaired (to <i>mAmh</i>)	ND
85 (5)	c.704C>T; p.Pro235Leu*	Higher	ND	ND	Atypical
86 (36)	c.712G>A; p.Asp238Asn	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
87 (33)	c.712G>A; p.Asp238Asn	ND	ND	ND	ND
88 (39)	c.763C>T; p.Arg255Cys	ND	ND	ND	ND
89 (40)	c.764G>T; p.Arg255Leu	Similar	ND	Impaired (to <i>CYP11A</i>)	ND
90 (31)	c.779C>T; p.Ala260Val	ND	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
91 (33)	c.800G>A; p.Arg267Lys	ND	ND	ND	ND
92 (33)	c.808G>A; p.Asp270Asp	ND	ND	ND	ND
93 (26)	c.842G>C; p.Arg281Pro	ND	ND	ND	ND
94 (2)	c.842G>C; p.Arg281Pro	Similar	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
95 (12)	c.847T>C; p.Cys283Arg	ND	Nucleus	ND	ND
96 (35)	c.877G>A; p.Asp293Asn*	ND	ND	ND	ND
97 (11)	c.877G>A; p.Asp293Asn*	Similar	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
98 (41)	c.887C>T; p.Thr296Met*	ND	ND	ND	ND
99 (9)	c.902G>A; p.Cys301Tyr*	Similar	ND	ND	ND
100 (42)	c.909C>G; p.Ser303Arg	ND	ND	ND	Atypical
101 (43)	c.910G>A; p.Glu304Lys	ND	ND	ND	ND
102 (18)	c.928C>G; p.His310Asp	ND	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
103 (19)	c.937C>T; p.Arg313Cys*	Similar	ND	ND	ND

LBD

104 (2)	c.937C>T; p.Arg313Cys*	Similar	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
105 (41)	c.937C>T; p.Arg313Cys*	ND	ND	ND	ND
106 (42)	c.938G>A; p.Arg313His*	ND	ND	ND	Atypical
107 (11)	c.974T>C; p.Leu325Pro	Similar	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
108 (11)	c.982G>A; p.Gly328Arg	Similar	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
109 (21)	c.982G>T; p.Gly328Trp	ND	ND	ND	ND
110 (44)	c.983G>T; p.Gly328Val	ND	ND	ND	ND
111 (11)	c.1018G>A; p.Ala340Thr	Reduced	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
112 (21)	c.1052C>A; p.Ala351Glu	ND	ND	ND	ND
113 (45)	c.1063G>A; p.Val355Met	ND	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
114 (2)	c.1063G>A; p.Val355Met	Similar	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
115 (29)	c.1073T>C; p.Leu358Pro	ND	ND	ND	Atypical
116 (2)	c.1082T>C; p.Leu361Pro	Similar	Cytoplasm	ND	Typical
117 (18)	c.1090G>T; p.Asp364Tyr	ND	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
118 (13)	c.1100A>G; p.Glu367Gly	Reduced	Nucleus	ND	ND
119 (13)	c.1109G>A; p.Cys370Tyr*	Reduced	Nucleus	ND	ND
120 (44)	c.1126C>T; p.Leu376Phe	ND	ND	ND	ND
121 (2)	c.1138G>T; p.Asp380Tyr	Similar	Extranuclear foci	ND	Typical
122 (4)	c.1198G>A; p.Ala400Thr	ND	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
123 (8)	c.1259T>C; p.Leu420Pro	ND	ND	ND	ND
124 (21)	c.1279C>T; p.Arg427Trp*	ND	ND	ND	ND
125 (13)	c.1289G>T; p.Ser430Ile	Reduced	Nucleus	ND	ND

126 (3)		c.1310T>A; p.Leu437Gln	ND	Nucleus	Normal	ND
127 (2)		c.1310T>A; p.Leu437Gln	Similar	Nucleus	ND	Atypical
128 (21)	C ^{ter}	c.1379A>G; p.Gln460Arg*	ND	ND	ND	ND

DBD, DNA binding domain; EMSA, Electrophoretic Mobility-Shift Assay; HR, hinge region; IF, immunofluoresce; LBD, ligand binding domain; ND, not determined; wt, wild-type; ter, terminus. ³Compared to wt.

Supplementary table 3. Clinical and genetic characterization of patients with *NR5A1*/SF-1 missense variants.

Study number	Location	<i>NR5A1</i> /SF-1 variant, (ACMG classification)	Karyotype	Genetic approach/Other variants ⁴	Sex assignment/reassignment (age)	Phenotype	Anomalies in other organs or cancer
1 (1)	N-ter	c.13T>G; p.Tyr5Asp, (VUS)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	19y, irregular menses with subsequent secondary amenorrhea. US: hypoplastic uterus, non-detectable ovaries.	No
2 (2)		c.17A<G; p.Asp8Gly, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	16y, female external genitalia with Mullerian structures and streak gonads. Normal adrenal phenotype.	No
3 (3)	DBD	c.43G>A; p.Val15Met, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	At birth, female external genitalia and bilateral palpable testes in labia. Histology: small gonads with well-formed testicular tissue and abundant seminiferous tubules. No Müllerian structures.	No
4 (2)		c.43G>A; p.Val15Met, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Small bilateral testes in labia, epididymis and vas deferens were present.	No
5 (4)		c.43G>A; p.Val15Met, (P)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	Secondary amenorrhea and POI diagnosis occurred following termination of oral contraceptives.	No
6 (5, 6)		c.58G>C; p.Val20Leu*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA+WES/ <i>INHA</i> (c.675T>G, Ser225Arg, Pa)	Female/male (1y)	Scrotal hypospadias and bilateral cryptorchidism. No Müllerian ducts.	No
7 (7)		c.64G>A; p.Gly22Ser*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Penoscrotal hypospadias and bifid scrotum.	No
8 (8)	c.65G>A; p.Gly22Asp*, (P)	46, XY	SGA+TGP/No	Female	Partially virilized and absence of Müllerian structures.	No	
9 (5)	c.70C>T; p.His24Tyr*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female/male (18 years)	At birth, ambiguous external genitalia. Puberty, progressive virilization, nonpalpable gonads. No Müllerian ducts. 19y, cryptorchidism, dysgenetic testes. Normal adrenal function.	No	
10 (9)	c.71A>T; p.His24Leu*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA+TGP/No	Male	At birth, micropenis, hypospadias, palpable gonads. Absence of Müllerian ducts. 2y, biopsy, at histology: testicular tissue. 17y, biopsy, at histology: absence of germ cells and Leydig cells hypoplasia. 10y, penis: 2.6cm. 14y, penis: 5.5cm, scrotal testes. 38y, penis: 3–4 cm.	No	
11 (10)	c.74A>G; p.Tyr25Cys, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Penoscrotal hypospadias and bifid scrotum.	No	

12 (11)	c.76G>A; p.Gly26Arg*, (P)	46, XY	TGP/No	Male	Perineal hypospadias, curved penis, penoscrotal transposition and bifid scrotum.	No
13 (12)	c.77G>C; p.Gly26Ala, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Childhood, female external genitalia and clitoromegaly in childhood. Adolescence, primary amenorrhea.	No
14 (13)	c.86C>A; p.Tyr29Lys, (P)	46, XY	TGP+WES/AR (c.884T>C; p.Leu295Pro, Pa); <i>MYH6</i> (c. C>T; Ala1411Thr, VUS)	Male	Micropenis, perineal hypospadias, bilateral cryptorchidism. 19y, penis straightening, bilateral orchidopexy, hypospadias surgery and scrotal fusion.	No
15 (9)	c.88T>A; p.Cys30Ser*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA+TGP/STAR (c.361C>T; p.Arg121Trp; VUS)	Male	At birth, curved micropenis, chordee with scrotal hypospadias and bilateral cryptorchidism. Surgical correction. 12y, penis 7.6 cm, testicular volume (MR):3.2mL and 3.3mL. 15y, penile size is normal.	Epididymal cysts (6.4mm, 2.7mm)
16 (5)	c.90T>G; p.Cys30Trp*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Ambiguous external genitalia, bilateral inguinal hernia. No Müllerian ducts. Seminiferous tubules devoid of spermatogonia.	No
17 (14)	c.95G>A; p.Ser32Asn, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	4m, genital ambiguity, phallus (4cm) with chordee, penoscrotal hypospadias and labioscrotal gonads. Genitography: blind ending vagina, no uterus. 6y, correction of hypospadias. 29y, spontaneous puberty, gynecomastia,	No
18 (15)	c.95G>A; p.Ser32Asn, (P)	46, XY	TGP/No	Female	Ambiguous external genitalia, inguinal/labioscrotal testes.	No
19 (7)	c.95G>A; p.Ser32Asn, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Proband 1: female; proband 2: male	Proband 1 with ambiguous genitalia, proband 2 with a milder phenotype, showing only micropenis and penoscrotal hypospadias. All showed normal adrenal steroid biosynthesis.	No
20 (16)	c.98G>C; p.Cys33Ser, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Clitoromegaly, urogenital sinus, inguinal gonads, no uterus. Histology: bilateral testes, Sertoli rich, few spermatogonia and Leydig cells.	No
21 (2)	c.98G>C; p.Cys33Ser, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Ambiguous external genitalia, clitoromegaly, bilateral inguinal gonads, urogenital sinus, fused labioscrotal folds. No Mullerian structures. Normal adrenal phenotype.	No
22 (17)	c.104G>A; p.Gly35Asp*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	2m, failure to thrive, frequent vomiting, skin hyperpigmentation. 4y, inguinal hernioplasty. US: uterus present.	Adrenal failure

23 (15)	c.104G>A; p.Gly35Asp*, (P)	46, XY	TGP/No	Male	Micropenis, hypospadias, bilateral cryptorchidism. 4y, bilateral testicular fixation. 4y and 8y, hCG treatment	No
24 (18)	c.104G>A; p.Gly35Asp*, (P)	46, XY	TGP/No	Female	Clitorohypertrophy, perineal hypospadias, bilateral inguinal gonads. No Müllerian structures. Histology: bilateral Leydig cell hypoplasia.	No
25 (13)	c.104G>T; p.Gly35Val, (P)	46, XY	TGP+WES/ <i>BMP2</i> (c.316G>A; Ala106Thr, VUS)	Male	Micropenis, hypospadias, bilateral cryptorchidism. 4y, bilateral testicular fixation. 4y and 8y, hCG treatment	No
26 (17)	c.106T>C; p.Phe36Leu, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	At birth, clitoromegaly (1.5cm), laparoscopy and US: no uterus, dysplastic testes with signs of microlithiasis. 10y, gonadectomy.	No
27 (14)	c.115C>T; p.Arg39Cys, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female/male (5m)	37d, genital ambiguity, 1.5 m phallus and inguinal gonads. US: inguinal gonads, no Müllerian derivatives.	No
28 (19)	c.116G>C; p.Arg39Pro, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Penoscrotal hypospadias, ambiguous genitalia, phallus (20mm), testicular volume: 20mm. Surgery: vaginal rest (15mm).	No
29 (2)	c.116G>C; p.Arg39Pro, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Ambiguous genitalia, PraderIII, clitoromegaly, phallus 2cm, penoscrotal hypospadias, labioscrotal testes (20mm). No Mullerian structures. Normal adrenal phenotype.	No
30 (20)	c.118A>C; p.Thr40Pro, (P)	46, XY	WES/No	Female/male (childhood)	At birth, ambiguous genitalia, prominent labioscrotal folds with palpable gonads, micropenis (1.3cm). Urogenitoscopy: normal bladder, small vagina, unclear uterine structures. Laparoscopy: hypoplastic testicular gonads, no Müllerian remnants. Histology: neonatal testicular appearance with germ cells. Spermogram: azoospermia. In childhood, hypospadias repair, orchidopexy and scrotal fusion. 10y, testicular volume: 3cc, Tanner stage G2.	No
31 (21)	c.119C>G; p.Thr40Arg, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	At birth, ambiguous external genitalia, scrotal hypospadias, micropenis (1–1.5cm), bifid scrotum, non-palpable gonads. Prader stage III. US: intraabdominal gonads (right, 0.85cm; left 0.95cm), no müllerian remnants.	No
32 (22)	c.122T>G; p.Val41Gly, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	At birth, clitoromegaly. 12y, no development of secondary sexual characteristics and clitoromegaly. Breast development: Tanner stage I. No posterior labial fusion, vaginal and urethral orifices separated. Presumed gonads were palpable bilaterally in the guinal region. No adrenal failiure.	No

33 (21)	c.140A>G; p.Tyr47Cys, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	At birth, ambiguous external genitalia, clitoris hypertrophy (1.5cm), partial labial fusion with a single penoscrotal urethral opening, and nonpalpable gonads. Prader stage III and EMS 4. Genitography: urogenital sinus, vagina (4cm), no uterus. Laparotomy: inguinal testes. Histology: testicular tissue with an infantile tubular component with Leydig-like differentiation. 1m, clitoroplasty and vaginoplasty. 4m, gonadectomy. 11y, hormonal replacement therapy and normal breast development	No
34 (11)	c.142A>C; p.Tyr48Pro, (VUS)	46, XY	TGP/No	Female	Perineal hypospadias, no vagina, uterus or gonads. Prader stage II.	No
35 (23)	c.162C>A; p.Ser54Arg, (VUS)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	20y, secondary amenorrhea.	No
36 (11)	c.163T>G; p.Cys55Gly, (P)	46, XY	TGP/No	Male	4y, hypospadias, well-developed bilateral testes.	No
37 (24)	c.184C>T; p.Arg62Cys, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Severe hypoplastic phallus, penile hypospadias, hypoplastic scrotum and impalpable gonads. US, two inguinal small testes (8–9 mm), no Müllerian structures. Orchidopexy, correction of hypospadias.	No
38 (25)	c.187A>C; p.Lys63Gln, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	6y, isolated micropenis.	No
39 (14)	c.194G>A; p.Cys65Tyr*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	First sibling: female/male (9months); second sibling: male; third sibling: male.	First sibling: 9m, ambiguous genitalia, US: no mullerian derivatives. Second sibling: 10y, ambiguous genitalia, penoscrotal hypospadias and labioscrotal gonads. No mullerian derivatives. Third sibling: 9y, ambiguous genitalia, perineal hypospadias, inguinal gonads. US: no mullerian derivatives. In all siblings: hypospadias repair, spontaneous puberty, adrenal function was normal.	No
40 (11)	c.205C>G; p.Arg69Gly, (LP)	46, XY	TGP/No	Male	Bifid scrotum, inguinal bilateral testes, small penis. No uterus, testes developed well.	No
41 (11)	c.206G>A; p.Arg69His, (LP)	46, XY	TGP/No	Male	6y, Prader stage III. No uterus, ovaries or fallopian tubes, inguinal bilateral dysplastic testes.	No
42 (3)	c.234G>A; p.Met78Ile, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	At birth, normal female external genitalia, inguinal testes. 7m, gonadectomy. Histology: small testes with seminiferous tubules, scarce	No

					germ cells, and well-developed vasa deferentia and epididymes. Interstitial cells vacuolated. Müllerian duct remnants are present.	
43 (2)	c.234G>A; p.Met78Ile, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Small bilateral inguinal testes (tubules present, germ cells scarce, vacuolated interstitial cells), epididymis and vas deferens present. Remnant Mullerian structures. Normal adrenal function.	No
44 (26)	c.234G>A; p.Met78Ile, (P)		SGA/No		Described in (3).	
45 (27)	c.250C>T; p.Arg84Cys*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	At birth, normal external genitalia. 11m, slight clitoromegaly and posterior labial fusion, inguinal gonads. 17m, gonadectomy. Histology: atrophic deferent ducts and epididymides, seminiferous tubules containing immature Sertoli cells and decreased germ cells, prominent interstitial Leydig cells. Genitography: blind vaginal pouch and urogenital sinus. Laparotomy: no Müllerian derivatives. 3y, feminizing genitoplasty. Adrenal function is normal.	No
46 (16)	c.251G>A; p.Arg84His*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	17y, clitoromegaly, urogenital sinus, inguinal gonads. No uterus, epididymis and vas deferens present. Histology: Bilateral testes.	No
47 (2)	c.251G>A; p.Arg84His*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	17y, clitoromegaly, urogenital sinus, fused labioscrotal folds, absence of Mullerian structures, bilateral inguinal testes, epididymis and vas deferens present. Normal adrenal function.	No
48 (18)	c.251G>A; p.Arg84His*, (P)	46, XY	TGP/ZFPM2 (c.A2107C; p.Met703Leu, VUS)	Female	Clitoromegaly, vaginal pouch, non-palpable right gonad, left is inguinal. Normal adrenal function.	No
49 (5, 6)	c.268G>C; p.Gly90Arg*, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA+WES/CACNG4 (c.715C>T, Arg239Trp, Pa); FBLN2 (c.385G>A, Asp129Asn, Pa); NAV1 (c.2947C>A,Pro983Thr, Pa); SMAD6 (c.1455dupC,Cys486Le ufsTer79, Pa); SRA1 (c.94C>G,Gln32Glu, Pa); ZDHHC11 (c.676G>A,Val226Met,	Female	Ambiguous external genitalia, bilateral inguinal hernia. No Müllerian ducts. Histology: Seminiferous tubules devoid of spermatogonia.	No

Pa), <i>ZFPM2</i> (c.302G>A, Gly101Glu, Pa)						
50 (15)	c.272G>A; p.Gly91Asp, (LP)	46, XY	TGP/No	Male	8y, hypospadias, inguinal and labioscrotal testes, no Müllerian structures.	No
51 (3)	c.271G>A; p.Gly91Ser*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Clitoral enlargement, labioscrotal gonads, remnant Müllerian structures.	No
52 (2)	c.271G>A; p.Gly91Ser*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Clitoromegaly (1cm), single perineal opening, labioscrotal testes (abundant tubules, Sertoli cells, germ cells, tubule density reduced in some areas), epididymis and vas deferens present. Remnant Mullerian structures. Normal adrenal function.	No
53 (28)	c.275G>A; p.Arg92Gln*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	1d, hypoglycemic convulsion, hyperpigmentation, progressive hypotonia, jaundice, weight loss, and failure to thrive developed during the neonatal period. 15d, primary adrenal failure. Abdominal CT: left adrenal hypoplasia and right adrenal agenesis. MRI: uterus present.	Adrenal failure
54 (3)	c.275G>A; p.Arg92Gln*, (P)		SGA/No		Described in (28).	
55 (2)	c.275G>A; p.Arg92Gln*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	First patient: female; second patient: male/female(ND)	First patient: 36y, adrenal failure. Female external genitalia, uterus. Second patient: normal external genitalia, absence of Müllerian structures, normal gonads. Normal adrenal function.	1st patient: adrenal failure.
56 (29)	c.275G>A; p.Arg92Gln*, (P)	46, XX	SGA/No	Male	In childhood, genitoplasty. 59y, non-palpable gonads, absence of Müllerian structures.	No
57 (30)	c.274C>T; p.Arg92Trp*, (P)	46, XX and 46, XY	WES, WGS/No	Females and males	6 family members: two diagnosed as 46,XX OT-DSD, three as 46,XX T-DSD and one as 46,XY PGD.	No
58 (31)	c.274C>T; p.Arg92Trp*, (P)	46, XX	TGP/Pat 1: <i>CREBBP</i> (c.1537C>A;p.Leu513Ile, Pa); <i>GDF9</i> (c.307C>T; p.Pro103Ser, Pa); <i>HSD3B1</i> (c.674A>G; p.Tyr225Cys, Pa); <i>STAR</i> (c.820C>T; p.Arg274Cys, Pa); <i>TG</i> (c.455G>A;		Patient 1: microphallus, penile hypospadias, small testes (1mL) located in scrotum or neck of scrotum. Histology: bilateral testes, absence of Müllerian structures. Azoospermic. Patient 2: Microphallus, perineal hypospadias, inguinal gonads. Histology: bilateral ovotestes and absence of Müllerian structures.	Patient 1: cardiac murmur, azoospermic; patient 2: intratubular neoplasia.

					p.Arg152His, Pa); Pat 2: AR (c.1174C>T; p.Pro392Ser, Pa), DACH1 (c.345C>A; p.Asn115Lys, B); ZFPM2 (c.292G>A; p.Asp98Asn, VUS); Pat 3: FRAS1 (c.9806G>A; p.Arg3269Gln), MTSS1 (c.1187T>C; p.Ile396Thr, B)	
59 (32)	c.308G>A; p.Arg103Gln*, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	13y, delayed puberty. US and CT: asplenia, bilateral inguinal testes, and absence of uterus, ovaries, and fallopian tubes. Gonadectomy. Histology: normal and abundant Sertoli cells, few Leydig cells, absence of germinal or pregerminal cells, absence of staining for premalignant markers.	Asplenia
60 (33)	c.340C>T; p.Arg114Trp, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	36y, idiopathic infertility, testicular volume: 8mL. Sperm count: azoospermia.	No
61 (34)	c.341G>A; p.Arg114Gln, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Adolescence, late vanishing testis.	No
62 (4)	c.368G>C; p.Gly123Ala, (VUS)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	Regular Menstration.Pregnancy with oocyte donation.	No
63 (35)	c.368G>C; p.Gly123Ala, (VUS)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	Hypertrophic clitoris, gonads located in pelvis.	No
64 (23)	c.386C>T; p.Pro129Leu, (VUS)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	25y, secondary amenorrhea.	No
65 (4)	c.386C>T; p.Pro129Leu, (VUS)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	25y, amenorrhea.	No
66 (35)	c.386C>T; p.Pro129Leu	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	Hypertrophic clitoris, gonads located in pelvis.	No
67 (36)	c.392C>T; p.Pro131Leu, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	41y, reduced sperm counts, infertility.	No

HR

68 (4)	c.407C>T; p.Pro136Leu, (LB)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	32y, regular menstruation.	No
69 (7)	c.428G>A; p.Ser143Asn, (VUS)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	Ambiguous genitalia	No
70 (37)	c.437G>C; p.Gly146Ala*, (B)	46, XX and 46, XY	SGA/No	Females and males	Thirty patients with several adrenal disorders. 8 patients with CS, 3 patients with PCS, 4 with NFAD, 6 patients with primary aldosteronism, 3 patients with AHC + HH, 1 female patient with AI and congenital Addison's disease, 5 patients with 17-OH deficiency.	21 with adrenal adenoma
71 (2)	c.437G>C; p.Gly146Ala*, (B)	46, XY	SGA/absence of Yq, microdeletion including <i>RBMY</i> and <i>DAZ</i>	Male	Normal size penis or micropenis, normal testes or cryptorchidism, absence of Müllerian structures. Normal adrenal phenotype.	No
72 (27)	c.437G>C; p.Gly146Ala*, (B)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	Clitoromegaly, posterior labial fusion, inguinal gonads, atrophic deferent ducts and epididymides, blind vaginal pouch and urogenital sinus. Seminiferous tubules containing immature Sertoli cells and decreased germ cells, prominent interstitial Leydig cells. No Mullerian derivatives. 3y, feminizing genitoplasty.	No
73 (24)	c.460G>A; p.Ala154Thr, (LB)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	4y, hypoplastic anchored phallus (penile length 2.5cm) and penile hypospadias. Descended normal testes. Hypospadias was surgically corrected. Normal adrenal function.	No
74 (2)	c.493G>C; p.Gly165Arg, (LB)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Male external genitalia, normal testes, absence of Müllerian structures. Oligozoospermia. Normal adrenal phenotype.	No
75 (15)	c.503C>A; p.Ala168Glu, (VUS)	46, XY	TGP/No	Female	9y, ambiguous external genitalia, testes inguinal and labioscrotal.	No
76 (33)	c.517G>A; p.Val173Met, (LB)	46, XY		Male	43y, idiopathic infertility. Low sperm count.	No
77 (36)	c.571C>T; p.Arg191Cys, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	25y, spermatogenic failure. Low sperm count.	No
78 (23)	c.593C>T; p.Pro198Leu,	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	33y, secondary amenorrhea.	No

	(VUS)						
79 (33)	c.598C>T; p.Pro200Ser, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	At birth, cryptorchidism.	No	
80 (33)	c.628C>T; p.Pro210Ser, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	At birth, cryptorchidism.	No	
81 (33)	c.632A>G; p.Tyr211Cys, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	37y, idiopathic infertility, testicular volume: 11mL, low sperm count.	No	
82 (36)	c.634G>A; p.Gly212Ser, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	37y, low sperm count.	No	
83 (13)	c.634G>A; p.Gly212Ser, (LP)	46, XY	TGP+WES/SRY (c. C>A; Arg76Leu, LP); <i>FGF10</i> (c. T>C; Met204Val, VUS)	Female	Primary amenorrhoea, minimal breast development, vulvar dysplasia, no testis and uterus. Infertility.	No	
84 (38)	c.689T>G; p.Leu230Arg, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	ND	14, primary amenorrhea, clitoromegaly, virilization and severe hirsutism. Fully developed axillary and pubertal hair (Tanner stages B1A2P6).	Lipomastia in the presence of obesity (BMI 31 kg/m2).	
85 (5)	c.704C>T; p.Pro235Leu*, (LP)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	At birth, normal female. 16y, US: prepubertal uterus, non-detectable ovaries. Normal adrenal function.	No	
86 (36)	c.712G>A; p.Asp238Asn, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	41y, spermatogenic failure.	No	
87 (33)	c.712G>A; p.Asp238Asn, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	47y, idiopathic infertility, low sperm count.	No	
88 (39)	c.763C>T; p.Arg255Cys, (LP)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	25y, POI, subnormal breast development, no visible external genital abnormalities.	No	
89 (40)	c.764G>T; p.Arg255Leu, (P)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	14m, adrenal insufficiency, seizures, severe slackness and muscular hypotonia.	Adrenal insufficiency	

90 (31)	c.779C>T; p.Ala260Val, (VUS)	46, XX	TGP/BMP15 (c.782_783delinsTCT; p.Ser261delinsSerLeu, ND); MSX2 (c.95A>T; p.Glu32Val, B); PGR (c.662T>A; p.Val221Asp, Pa); POR (c.1709G>A; p.Arg570His, Pa); PTCH1 (c.1612G>C; p.Gly538Arg, Pa); RARA (c.128C>G; p.Thr43Ser, B)	Male/female(4y)	Ambiguous genitalia, small phallus and vagina (4 cm deep), separate urethral and vaginal openings. The right gonad was an ovotestis with sporadic germ cells in the tubules, calcifications, and primordial follicles in ovarian part. The left gonad had ovarian tissue with both primordial and developing follicles.	No
91 (33)	c.800G>A; p.Arg267Lys, (LB)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	41y, azoospermia with history of unilateral cryptorchidism. Testicular volume: 10mL.	No
92 (33)	c.808G>A; p.Asp270Asp, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	36y, azoospermia with history of unilateral cryptorchidism. Testicular volume: 7mL.	No
93 (26)	c.842G>C; p.Arg281Pro, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	At birth, posterior hypospadias, bifid scrotal folds, palpable gonads, penis was buried and angled. No Mullerian derivatives. Spontaneous puberty. Adrenal insufficiency was discarded.	No
94 (2)	c.842G>C; p.Arg281Pro, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Hypospadias, bifid scrotum, micropenis, chordee, palpable gonads (33-35mm). No Müllerian structures. Normal adrenal phenotype	No
95 (12)	c.847T>C; p.Cys283Arg, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	7y, female external genitalia. Inguinal testes and no Müllerian structures. Adrenal insufficiency was discarded.	No
96 (35)	c.877G>A; p.Asp293Asn*, (P)	46, XY and 46,XX	SGA/No	Females	18y, primary amenorrhea and signs of virilization. Sister: 19y, primary amenorrhea.	No
97 (11)	c.877G>A; p.Asp293Asn*, (P)	46, XY	TGP/No	Male	3m, penoscrotal transposition, bifid scrotum, scrotal bilateral testes.	No
98 (41)	c.887C>T; p.Thr296Met*, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	At birth, perineal hypospadias and palpable testes. Adrenal insufficiency.	Adrenal insufficiency

99 (9)	c.902G>A; p.Cys301Tyr*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA+TGP/No	Female	14y, primary amenorrhea, stenotic and enlarged vagina. 15y, at laparoscopy: rudimentary uterus, streak gonads. Gonadectomy, at histology: testicular parenchyma, normal fallopian tubes.	No
100 (42)	c.909C>G; p.Ser303Arg, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Perineal hypospadias, EMS 8/12. At Puberty: prepuberty, fertility as prepubertal.	No
101 (43)	c.910G>A; p.Glu304Lys, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Males	Male siblings with isolated severe hypospadias. The father is asymptomatic with preserved fertility.	No
102 (18)	c.928C>G; p.His310Asp, (LP)	46, XY	TGP/No	Males	Male siblings with proximal hypospadias, micropenis and palpable bilateral gonads. Retained Müllerian remnants.	No
103 (19)	c.937C>T; p.Arg313Cys*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	At birth, glandular hypospadias, micropenis, scrotal testes (18mm).	No
104 (2)	c.937C>T; p.Arg313Cys*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Male external genitalia, glandular hypospadias, normal phallus (3.3*1.5cm) and scrotal testes (18mm in scrotum). Normal adrenal phenotype.	No
105 (41)	c.937C>T; p.Arg313Cys*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	At birth, scrotal hypospadias, micropenis (2cm), bilateral scrotal gonads. No Müllerian ducts.	No
106 (42)	c.938G>A; p.Arg313His*, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Perineal hypospadias. Spontaneous puberty and preserved fertility.	No
107 (11)	c.974T>C; p.Leu325Pro, (VUS)	46, XY	TGP/No	Female	11m, penoscrotal transposition, bifid scrotum, curved penis perineal hypospadias, small testes.	No
108 (11)	c.982G>A; p.Gly328Arg, (P)	46, XY	TGP/No	Female	1y, cryptorchidism of the right teste and dysplasia of the left teste.	No
109 (21)	c.982G>T; p.Gly328Trp, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female/male(NA)	At birth, external ambiguous genitalia, micropenis, perineal hypospadias and labioscrotal folds without palpable gonads. 20d, stretched penile length (1.5cm). Prader stage III and EMS 5.	No
110 (44)	c.983G>T; p.Gly328Val, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	In early infancy, correction of hypospadias. 28y, severe penoscrotal hypospadias, hypoplastic phallus, and small inguinal testes. Testosterone substitution was started.	No
111 (11)	c.1018G>A; p.Ala340Thr, (VUS)	46, XY	TGP/No	Female	Cryptorchidism of the right teste and dysplasia of the left teste.	No

112 (21)	c.1052C>A; p.Ala351Glu, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	6m, labial palpable mass on the right side, clitoris hypertrophy. Prader stage II and EMS 4. Genitography: urogenital sinus with a normal vagina length (7cm). Laparoscopy: müllerian remnants and inguinal right gonad present. Histology: bilateral atrophic testis with hypotrophic Leydig cells. 10y, started hormonal replacement therapy with ethynil-E2. Normal breast development. Adrenal insufficiency was discarded.	No
113 (45)	c.1063G>A; p.Val355Met, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	13y, micropenis at neonatal age, unilateral atrophied teste. Absence of Mullerian structures	No
114 (2)	c.1063G>A; p.Val355Met, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	Male external genitalia, micropenis (1.8*0.8cm), only one inguinal atrophied teste. No Müllerian structures. Normal adrenal phenotype.	
115 (29)	c.1073T>C; p.Leu358Pro, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	4y, atypical external genitalia, perineal hypospadias, palpable gonads. No Müllerian structures. Gonadectomy and genitoplasty.	No
116 (2)	c.1082T>C; p.Leu361Pro, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	4y, female external genitalia. Small inguinal testes and not determined Müllerian structures.	No
117 (18)	c.1090G>T; p.Asp364Tyr, (LP)	46, XY	TGP/No	Female	Female external genitalia, bilateral intra-abdominal gonads and rudimentary uterus. At histology: Right dysgenetic testis and left streak gonad. Gonadoblastoma.	Gonadoblastoma
118 (13)	c.1100A>G; p.Glu367Gly, (LP)	46, XY	TGP+WES/ <i>CST9</i> (c. G>A; p.Arg87*, VUS)	Male	10y, hypospadias repair. 28y, micropenis, penoscrotal hypospadias, unilateral cryptorchidism. Hypospadias repair and left testicular fixation.	No
119 (13)	c.1109G>A; p.Cys370Tyr*, (LP)	46, XY	TGP+WES/ <i>SOX3</i> (Val53Leu, LP)	Male	3y, micropenis, penoscrotal hypospadias, unilateral cryptorchidism. Hypospadias repair.	No
120 (44)	c.1126C>T; p.Leu376Phe, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	At puberty, clitoral hypertrophy. 14y, bilateral gonadectomy and estrogen substitution.	No
121 (2)	c.1138G>T; p.Asp380Tyr, (P)	46, XX	SGA/No	Female	At adolescence, female external genitalia, small gonads and uterus. Normal adrenal phenotype.	No
122 (4)	c.1198G>A; p.Ala400Thr, (VUS)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	31y, secondary amenorrhea.	No
123 (8)	c.1259T>C; p.Leu420Pro, (LP)	46, XY	SGA+TGP/No	Female	At puberty, virilization. Absence of Müllerian structures.	

124 (21)		c.1279C>T; p.Arg427Trp*, (LP)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	11y, Prader stage II and EMS 3. Painful inguinal left mass, appearance of pubarche, and mild clitoris hypertrophy. Small vaginal meatus, normal vagina size (7cm), palpable gonads. US: two inguinal gonads and no müllerian remnants. Laparoscopy: müllerian derivatives absent. Histology: testicular parenchyma with normal architecture of the tubules containing few germ cells spermatogonia, no spermatogenesis.	No
125 (13)		c.1289G>T; p.Ser430Ile, (LP)	46, XY	TGP+WES/ <i>HSD17B3</i> (c. A>G; Ile60Thr, Pa); <i>WT1</i> (c. T>G; Thr7Pro, Pa)	Male	16y, micropenis, hypospadias, cryptorchidism, gonadal dysplasia.	No
126 (3)		c.1310T>A; p.Leu437Gln, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	At birth, small phallus, severe penoscrotal hypospadias and chordee, palpable bilateral testes. In early infancy, 3 cycles of testost treatment (25mg). 14m, hypospadias repair. 6y, bilateral orchidopexy. Biopsy: separated hyalinized non-canalated seminiferous tubules with a predominantly Sertoli cell only pattern and few scattered germ cells. At late-childhood and adolescence, partial form of HH in addition to a primary testicular defect. 13y, Tanner G2, P1, A1, testicular volume: 4-5cc. Adrenal function was normal.	No
127 (2)		c.1310T>A; p.Leu437Gln, (P)	46, XY	SGA/No	Male	6y, ambiguous external genitalia, micropenis, penoscrotal hypospadias, chordee, scrotal testes. Absence of Müllerian structures.	No
128 (21)	C-ter	c.1379A>G; p.Gln460Arg, (LB)	46, XY	SGA/No	Female	4m, ambiguous external genitalia, phallus (2cm) with chordee, penoscrotal hypospadias and non-palpable gonads. Prader stage II-III and EMS. US: bilateral abdominal testis and no Müllerian derivatives. Genitography: urogenital sinus, no vagina and uterus. Histology: bilateral testicular dysgenesis, testicular tissue, small primitive tubules, no definite Leydig cells. 1y, gonadectomy. At 3 and 10y, vaginoplasty and clitoroplasty. At puberty: normal breast development and hair growth after estrogen treatment.	Severe scoliosis, prominent forehead. 19y, final height under the normal range.

AI, adrenal insufficiency; AHC, adrenal hypoplasia congenita; B, benign; CS, Cushing's syndrome; CT, computerized tomography; d, days; EMS, external masculinization score; E2, oestradiol; hCG, human chorionic gonadotropin; HH, hypogonadotropic hypogonadism; LP, likely pathogenic; m, month; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; ND, not determined; NFAD, nonfunctioning adrenocortical adenoma; OT-DSD, ovotesticular DSD; Pa, pathogenic; PCS, preclinical Cushing's syndrome; POI, primary ovarian insufficiency; SGA, single gene analysis; T-DSD, testicular DSD; TGP, targeted-gene panel; US, ultrasound; VUS, variant of unknown significance; WES, whole-exome sequencing; y, years. ⁴Pathogenicity according to the publication.

	2p16.3p16.3(50732444-50894316)x1			ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	
15	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.393G>A; p.Pro131= (rs769519459)	4	HR	0.00009855	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	1.620	ND
	16p13.11p13.11(15830681-16270149)x3			ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.393G>A; p.Pro131= (rs769519459)	4	HR	0.00009855	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	1.620	ND
16	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.437G>C; p.Gly146Ala	4	HR	0.7568	B	B	B	B	VUS	Prben	N	ND	0.217	B	
	Xq13.3.3q13.3(74380482-74567915)x2			ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
17	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.393G>A; p.Pro131= (rs769519459)	4	HR	0.00001252	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	1.620	ND
18	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.552del; p.Tyr185Thrfs*111	4	HR	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
19	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.555C>A; p.Tyr185*	4	HR	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	VUS	ND	ND	ND	ND	35	ND
20	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.632_668del; p.Tyr211Cysfs*73	4	HR	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
21	<i>POR</i> , c.859G>C; p.Ala287Pro (rs121912974)	9		0.0005195	P	VUS	VUS	ND	VUS	Prdam	ND	VUS	29.2	P	
	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.680T>C; p.Ile227Thr	4	LBD	ND	ND	P	VUS	Prdam	B	Prdam	N	P	25.4	P	
22	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.839C>A; p.Ala280Glu	4	LBD	ND	ND	P	P	Prdam	VUS	Prdam	Dis	P	26.5	P	
23	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.926A>T; p.Asp309Val	5	LBD	ND	ND	P	P	Prdam	VUS	Prdam	Dis	P	27.7	P	
24	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.946del; p.Gln316Serfs*18	5	LBD	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>FAT4</i> , c.686A>G; p.Tyr229Cys (rs139716832)	4		ND	VUS	P	P	Prdam	VUS	ND	ND	B	27.1	VUS	
25	<i>FAT4</i> , c.5278A>G; p.Ile1760Val (rs147872710)	9		ND	VUS	B	B	B	B	ND	ND	B	15.72	B	
	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.977T>C; p.Val326Ala	5	LBD	ND	ND	B	B	Prdam	VUS	Prdam	N	P	27.3	P	
26	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.985C>T; p.Gln329*	5	LBD	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	VUS	ND	ND	ND	53	ND	
27	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.985C>T; p.Gln329*	5	LBD	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	VUS	ND	ND	ND	53	ND	
28	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.991-1G>A	in5		ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	VUS	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	
29	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.992T>G; p.Val331Gly	6	LBD	ND	ND	VUS	P	Prdam	VUS	Psdam	Dis	P	29.5	P	
30	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1065_1066insTGCTGCAGCTGCTTGCGCTGG; p.Val355_Leu356insCysCysSerCysLeuArgTrp	6	LBD	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
31	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1105G>T; p.Val369Phe	6	LBD	ND	ND	VUS	VUS	Prdam	VUS	Prdam	Dis	P	27.6	P	
32	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1106_1109del; p.Val369Alafs*12	6	LBD	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
33	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.(1138+1_1139-1)(1386+1_1387-1)del; p.Asp380_Thr461del	7	LBD	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
34	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1139-2A>G	in6		ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	VUS	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
35	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1157_1211dup; p.Tyr404*	7	LBD	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	<i>DHX37</i> , c.904G>A; p.Gly302Ser (rs369888049)	6		0.0001507	ND	VUS	P	Prdam	VUS	Prdam	N	B	27.4	B	
36	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1211A>G; p.Tyr404Cys	7	LBD	ND	ND	P	P	Prdam	VUS	Prdam	Dis	P	29.2	P	
37	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1307A>G; p.Tyr436Cys	7	LBD	ND	VUS	P	P	Prdam	VUS	Prdam	Dis	P	27.2	P	
38	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1353G>A; p.Leu451= (rs79833327)	7	LBD	0.04740	B	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	11.02	ND	
	2p16.3 dup			ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
39	<i>NR5A1</i> , c.1379A>T; p.Gln460Leu (rs146454575)	7	C-term	0.00005593	ND	VUS	VUS	B	B	Prben	Dis	VUS	23.7	B	
	<i>SOX10</i> , c.1241A>C; p.His414Pro (rs748666965)	4		0.0001012	ND	VUS	P	Psdam	VUS	Prdam	Dis	VUS	23.4	VUS	
	<i>SOX10</i> , c.1284G>T; p.Met428Ile (rs777737385)	4		0.0001015	ND	VUS	VUS	Psdam	VUS	Prdam	Dis	VUS	26.0	VUS	

B, benign; DBD, DNA binding domain; Dis, disease; HR, hinge region; in, intron; LBD, ligand binding domain; LP, MAF, Minor allele frequency corresponding to the highest MAF within the different populations in gnomAD, Likely pathogenic; N, neutral; ND, not determined; P, pathogenic; Prdam, probably damaging; Prben, probably benign; Psdam, possibly damaging; term, terminal; VUS, variant of unknown significance; ZFI, Zinc finger domain I; ZFII, Zinc finger domain.

Supplementary table 5. Primers sequences used for *NR5A1*/SF-1 gene amplification in PCR-based site-directed mutagenesis.

Patient	cDNA change, protein change	Sense (5' to 3')	Antisense (5' to 3')
2	c.37T>A, p.Cys13Ser	CTGGACGAGCTGAGCCCCGTGTGCG	CGCACACGGGGCTCAGCTCGTCCAG
3	c.40C>T, p.Pro14Ser	GACGAGCTGTGCTCCGTGTGCGGGG	CCCCGCACACGGAGCACAGCTCGTC
4	c.50G>T, p.Gly17Val	GCCCCGTGTGCGTGGACAAGGTGTC	GACACCTTGTCCACGCACACGGGGC
5	c.116G>T, p.Arg39Leu	AAGGGCTTCTTCAAGCTCACGGTGCAGAAACAAC	GTTGTTCTGCACCGTGAGCTTGAAGAAGCCCTT
6	c.208T>C, p.Phe70Leu	GTCCCTTCTGCCGCTCCAGAAATGCTG	CAGGCATTCTGGAGGCGGCAGAAAGGGAC
7 and 8	c.217T>A and c.218G>C, p.Cys73Ser	TTCTGCCGCTTCCAGAAATACCTGACGGTGG	CCACCGTCAGGTATTTCTGGAAGCGGCAGAA
9	c.218G>A, p.Cys73Tyr	TCTGCCGCTTCCAGAAATCCCTGACGGTG	CACCGTCAGGGATTTCTGGAAGCGGCAGA
10	c.219C>G, p.Cys73Trp	CGCTTCCAGAAATGGCTGACGGTGGGGAT	ATCCCCACCGTCAGCCATTTCTGGAAGCG
12	c.247G>A, p.Val83Met	CGCCTGGAAGCCATGCGCGCTGACC	GGTCAGCGCGCATGGCTTCCAGGCG
13	c.247G>A, p.Val83Leu	CGCCTGGAAGCCTTGC CGCTGACC	GGTCAGCGCGCAAGGCTTCCAGGCG
21	c.680T>C, p.Ile227Thr	AACGTGCCTGAGCTCACCTGCAGCTGC	GCAGCTGCAGGGTGAGCTCAGGCACGTT
22	c.839C>A, p.Ala280Glu	CATCGTGGACTGGGAACGCAGGTGCATGG	CCATGCACCTGCGTTCCAGTCCACGATG
29	c.992T>G, p.Val331Gly	CCGGGCAGGAGGGGGAGCTGACCAC	GTGGTCAGTCCCCCTCTGCCCGG
31	c.1105G>T, p.Val369Phe	GCTGGACCGGCAGGAGTTTTTCTGCCTCAA	TTGAGGCAGAAAACTCTGCCGGTCCAGC
36	c.1211A>G, p.Tyr404Cys	GCCCTGCTTGACTGCACCCTGTGCCAC	GTGGCACAGGGTGCAGTCAAGCAGGGC
39	c.1379A>T, p.Gln460Leu	GAAATGCTGCAAGCCAAGCTGACTTGA	TCAAGTCAGCTTGGCTTGCAGCATTTTC

Supplementary table 6. Primary and secondary antibodies used in the Western blot analysis

Primary antibody	Dilution used	Product number, supplier	Secondary antibody	Dilution used	Product number, supplier
Anti-HA	1:1000	11867423001, Roche	Goat anti rat (IRDye 800CW)	1:2500	926-32219, LICOR
β -Actin	1:2500	A1978, Sigma	Donkey anti mouse (IRDye 680RD)	1:2500	926-68972, LICOR
Lamin B1	1:1000	MAB85251, Novusbio		1:2500	
Rab11	1:1000	610657, BD-Transduction Laboratories	Goat anti mouse (IRDye 800CW)	1:2500	926-32210, LICOR

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